

Can we distinguish positive cooperativity from autocatalysis in enzyme kinetics?

Sharmistha Dhata^a, Kinshuk Banerjee^b and Kamal Bhattacharyya*^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail: pcsdhata@gmail.com, pchemkb@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, AJC Bose College, 1/1B, Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Road, Kolkata-700 020, India

E-mail: kbpchem@gmail.com

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Different graphical plots involving the catalytic rate and the (initial) substrate concentration exist in the enzyme kinetics literature to estimate the reaction constants. But, none of these standard plots can unambiguously distinguish between the two important mechanisms of rate enhancement: positive cooperativity among the active sites of an oligomeric enzyme and autocatalysis of the intermediate complex of an enzyme with a single active site. In the simplest situation of a direct autocatalysis, at least, we have achieved this distinction here by providing a nice linear plot for the latter. Importantly, to accomplish this task, no extra information other than the steady-state rate as a function of substrate concentration is required. In case of regression of the rate, a similar scheme can also distinguish negative cooperativity from autoinhibition.

Keywords: Enzyme kinetics, cooperativity, autocatalysis, steady state.

1. Introduction

Enzyme catalysis is a highly important biochemical reaction where specific substrates are efficiently converted into products¹. Investigations on the catalytic mechanisms span over a century. The Michaelis-Menten (MM) scheme² is a cornerstone in the field of theoretical modeling of enzyme kinetic data³. The rate of product formation in MM scheme under a steady-state approximation⁴ (SSA) of the intermediate complex plays the benchmark role in the analyses of kinetic constants. The SSA relies on the constancy of the concentration(s) of such complex(es) *over a considerable region of time* and insists that *experiments are carried out within this time interval*. This constancy of complex concentration arises, wherever appropriate, out of a balance between the rate of formation and rate of degradation of such species. To determine the rate parameters under this restriction, various ways of plotting the rate against (initial) substrate concentration are present in the literature with their respective advantages and disadvantages³. Some notable examples are the Lineweaver-Burk (LB), Eadie-Hofstee (EH) and Hanes-Woolf (HW) plots^{1,3}.

The MM scheme represents the simplest model of en-

zyme catalysis. Naturally, the enzyme is considered to have a single substrate binding site or active site. However, there are many enzymes in nature with multiple binding sites. Interactions among these sites lead to cooperativity⁵⁻⁷. As a result, one notices either an enhancement (positive cooperativity) or diminution (negative cooperativity) of the catalytic rate compared to that obtained from a MM scheme with equal number of binding sites acting independently, i.e. zero cooperativity⁸. A prime example of cooperative kinetics is the oxygen binding to haemoglobin^{9,10}. However, there exists another possible way of rate enhancement, e.g. through autocatalysis¹¹⁻¹⁶. This can also increase the rate compared to the MM case at similar substrate concentrations even for an enzyme with a single active site. Autocatalysis is thought to play crucial roles in the evolution of population¹⁴ as well as gene¹⁵. Here, we consider a simple case of *direct* autocatalysis¹⁶ of the intermediate complex. A reduction of rate may then refer to either negative cooperativity or autoinhibition.

We display in Fig. 1 the different schemes under investigation. The main point is an *enhancement of rate* relative to the MM one. However, once a particular mechanism operates after the substrate-enzyme mixing, we have only *one*

value for the rate. So, the 'enhancement' cannot be recognized. The issue, therefore, is to detect the kind of mechanism or scheme that is operative for a specific substrate-enzyme pair from rate data.

Scheme 1 :

Scheme 2 :

Scheme 3 :

Scheme 4 :

Fig. 1. Reaction schemes for the various cases considered. Scheme 1 (*abbr.* MM): Michaelis-Menten; Scheme 2 (*abbr.* Auto): autocatalysis of the intermediate; Scheme 3 (*abbr.* 2-site): cooperative kinetics for an enzyme with two active sites; Scheme 4 (*abbr.* 3-site): cooperative kinetics for an enzyme with three active sites. The factors '2' and '3' attached to certain rate constants account for the statistical weightage.

A well-known signature of MM kinetics under the SSA is the hyperbolic nature of the curve of the steady-state (SS), *constant* rate \bar{R} against the *average* substrate concentration $[\bar{S}]$ during the time over which the SSA is valid. This nature will be apparent from eq. (1) in Sec. 2. However, it is more usual to choose $[S]_0 \gg [E]_0$ so that $[\bar{S}]$ may be replaced by the starting substrate concentration $[S]_0$ without incurring any serious error. Now, both positive cooperativity and *direct* autocatalysis will show non-hyperbolic sigmoidal nature¹⁶ of the rate against $[S]_0$. Thus, these rate-enhancing mechanisms can be identified, in principle, as non-MM ones. In this context, it is important to clarify the case of monomeric enzymes with multiple conformations [*viz.* hysteretic¹⁷ and mnemonic¹⁸ enzymes] that can also exhibit cooperative kinetics. However, such cooperative (sigmoidal) behavior arises in open reaction systems reaching non-equilibrium steady states¹⁹.

For a system reaching chemical equilibrium, as in our case, the expression of rate resembles that of MM [see, e.g. Appendix 1, particularly eq. (A1) that looks closely like eq. (1) in Sec. 2]. Thus, catalysis by a monomeric enzyme [obeying Scheme 2 in Fig. 1] reaching equilibrium *can* show sigmoidal behavior due to autocatalysis²⁰, but certainly *not* via multiple conformations of the enzyme. Then, the important question to ask is: How shall we distinguish between autocatalysis and positive cooperativity, both showing non-MM sigmoidal kinetics, from catalytic rate measurements alone?

In this work, we show that none of the standard plots can unambiguously discriminate autocatalytic behavior from positive cooperativity. As a remedy, we introduce here an alternative graphical method that serves the purpose quite satisfactorily, at least in the simplest situation. In what follows, cooperativity stands for positive cooperativity only.

2. Experimental

2.1. The equations for SS rates

We determine the SS rates of product formation in all the cases. The calculations are based on the schemes shown in Fig. 1. In Appendix 2 [eq. (A4) to eq. (A17)], we outline the key steps of arriving at the SS rate \bar{R} for each of the cases dealt with below. Understandably, $[X]_0$ refers to the starting concentration of the species X and $[\bar{X}]$ denotes the *average* SS concentration of X over the period of validity of SSA. However, for further simplification, we specifically take $[E]_0 = 1 \mu\text{M}$ and $[S]_0 \geq 100 \mu\text{M}$ so that $[S]_0 \gg [E]_0$ is satisfied. This also ensures $[\bar{S}] \approx [S]_0$ in all the cases, since it is usual that a negligible amount of product is formed during the period over which SSA is valid.

2.1.1. MM kinetics

The SS rate of product formation [see eqs. (A4)–(A6) in Appendix 2] comes out as

$$\bar{R} = \frac{k_2[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K_M + [\bar{S}]} \quad (1)$$

The MM constant is $K_M = (k_{-1} + k_2)/k_1$. The conservations of enzyme and substrate concentrations are given by

$$[E]_0 = [E] + [ES]; [S]_0 = [S] + [ES] + [P] \quad (2)$$

2.1.2. Autocatalysis

In this case, the SS rate [see eqs. (A7)–(A9) in Appendix

2] is given as

$$\bar{R} = \frac{k_2[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K_M + [\bar{S}] - (k_0[\bar{E}][\bar{S}]/k_1)} \quad (3)$$

The conservation conditions are the same as given in eq. (2). Additionally, the first conservation equation in (2) tells us that [E] will be a constant under the SSA [denoted by \bar{E}] in eq. (3)] where [ES] remains also so by definition.

2.1.3. 2-site cooperativity

The expression of SS rate [see eqs. (A10)–(A13) in Appendix 2] for this scheme is

$$\bar{R} = \frac{2k_4[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K_M K_{M1} + 2K_{M1}[\bar{S}] + [\bar{S}]^2} (k_2 K_{M1}/k_4 + [\bar{S}]) \quad (4)$$

Here, $K_{M1} = (k_{-3} + k_4)/k_3$ and K_M is same as the one defined above for the MM case. The conservation relations used are

$$\begin{aligned} [E]_0 &= [E] + [ES_1] + [ES_2]; \\ [S]_0 &= [S] + [ES_1] + 2[ES_2] + [P] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

ously. The conservation relations are obtained as natural extensions of eq. (5):

$$\begin{aligned} [E]_0 &= [E] + [ES_1] + [ES_2] + [ES_3]; \\ [S]_0 &= [S] + [ES_1] + 2[ES_2] + 3[ES_3] + [P] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

2.2. The numerical experiments

The set of coupled nonlinear differential equations that follows from each scheme is solved stepwise via the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method²¹. The stability of the numerical experiment in each run is checked against the satisfaction of conservation equations. The time step has been fixed at 10^{-6} s. Each run corresponds to a fixed value for $[E]_0$ equal to $1 \mu\text{M}$. Everywhere, the starting value for $[S]_0$ is $100 \mu\text{M}$, but it is increased at regular intervals for different runs.

2.3. The sets

Two different sets are chosen by varying certain rate constants in accordance with Table 1. The choices are guided by the satisfaction of the SSA, as will be evident from Fig. 2 in Sec. 3.

Table 1. Values for the rate constants in the various schemes considered in Fig. 1. Here, k_1, k_3 and k_5 are in $(\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{s})^{-1}$, while k_0 is in $\mu\text{M}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and $k_{-1}, k_2, k_{-3}, k_4, k_{-5}, k_6$ are all in s^{-1} . For each set, the different cases correspond to the abbreviated schemes indicated in Fig. 1 of the main text

Set	Case	k_1	k_{-1}	k_2	k_0	k_3	k_{-3}	k_4	k_5	k_{-5}	k_6
1	MM	0.1	200	0.01	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	Auto	0.01	500	2.5	0.1	–	–	–	–	–	–
	2-site	0.008	500	1.0	–	0.05	100	1.1	–	–	–
	3-site	0.006	500	1.0	–	0.02	100	1.1	0.05	100	1.2
2	MM	0.1	200	0.01	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	Auto	0.1	200	0.04	0.5	–	–	–	–	–	–
	2-site	0.2	250	0.01	–	0.25	200	0.0175	–	–	–
	3-site	0.2	350	0.01	–	0.25	325	0.0125	0.3	300	0.015

2.1.4. 3-site cooperativity

This scheme has a SS rate [see eqs. (A14)–(A17) in Appendix 2] of

$$\bar{R} = \frac{3k_6[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K_M K_{M1} K_{M2} + 3K_{M1} K_{M2}[\bar{S}] + 3K_{M2}[\bar{S}]^2 + [\bar{S}]^3} \times \left(\frac{k_2 K_{M1} K_{M2}}{k_6} + \frac{2k_4 K_{M2}[\bar{S}]}{k_6} + [\bar{S}]^2 \right) \quad (6)$$

Here, $K_{M2} = (k_{-5} + k_6)/k_5$ and K_M, K_{M1} are as defined previ-

3. Results and discussion

3.1. SS catalytic rates

We first highlight the time profiles of the rates for both the sets, following in each case (*cf.* Table 1) the various schemes outlined in Fig. 1. Note that the plots depicted in Fig. 2 ensure the validity of the SSA in *all* the situations under consideration [*cf.* our comments below eq. (A17) in Appendix 2]. Otherwise, observed rates R would not have quickly reached a constant value at \bar{R} , and stayed there for an appreciable time, in all the cases under study. At higher $[S]_0$, it is only

Fig. 2. Time-profile of the rate R for the two sets of rate constants (*cf.* Table 1) shown in (A) and (B). The horizontal lines correspond to constancy of the SS rates symbolized by \bar{R} .

natural that SSA will be better obeyed. Therefore, our theoretical analyses by invoking the SSA find the due justification.

Here and elsewhere, we consistently denote the MM case by a black line, autocatalysis by a red dotted line, 2-site cooperativity by a green dotted line and the 3-site one by a blue dotted line. Let us note in addition that, by virtue of Fig. 2, an *a posteriori* justification of *our choice* of rate constants summarized in Table 1 is immediately found.

3.2. The non-MM behavior

The nature of variation of the SS catalytic rate \bar{R} with $[S]_0$ can give a clear indication of non-MM behavior if one studies such reactions by systematically increasing the latter. The curve is *hyperbolic* for MM kinetics, but generally *sigmoidal* when the mechanism involves cooperativity or autocatalysis. This is evident from Fig. 3 for the two different choices of rate constants [see Table 1]. The sets provide appreciable differences in the SS rates compared with the bare MM mechanism (Scheme 1). It is also clear from Fig. 3 that

cooperativity and autocatalysis cannot be distinguished from each other, as already mentioned in Section 1.

However, one important point to mention is that, if the degree of cooperativity or autocatalysis is small, the sigmoidal nature of the curve may be difficult to identify. Hence, the curves for all the cases may appear similar, i.e. hyperbolic²². In such cases, and also generally, plots like HW²³, LB²⁴ and EH²⁵ may help us to distinguish the non-MM behavior. For example, in Fig. 4, we show the HW plots for all the cases taking the two sets of rate constants. The MM case has a positive slope throughout, whereas rest of the schemes have negative slopes at lower range of $[S]_0$. But, even these plots *cannot* distinguish cooperativity from autocatalysis. A similar conclusion follows from the observed LB and EH plots, as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. In both these cases, linearity will reveal, as before, the MM mechanism. But, autocatalysis cannot be identified unambiguously from them.

3.3. Discriminating autocatalysis from cooperativity

Having realized the problem, we now look for a very dif-

Fig. 3. Variation of the SS catalytic rate \bar{R} as a function of the starting substrate concentration $[S]_0$ for the different kinetic schemes with two different sets of rate constants (*cf.* Table 1) plotted in (A) and (B).

Fig. 4. Hanes-Woolf plots for the various schemes with two different sets of rate constants shown in (A) and (B). They cannot distinguish autocatalysis from positive cooperativity.

Fig. 5. Lineweaver-Burk plots for the two sets of rate constants shown in (A) and (B). They are also unable to discriminate between autocatalysis and positive cooperativity.

Fig. 6. Eadie-Hofstee plots for the two sets of rate constants shown in (A) and (B). They too cannot differentiate autocatalysis from positive cooperativity.

ferent graphical strategy. It necessitates the value of the SS rate when $[S]_0 \rightarrow \infty$. We call this quantity as R_∞ . It signifies the saturated catalytic rate^{22,26}. A cursory glance at Fig. 3 will uncover that such values are not difficult to estimate via extrapolation techniques. They can also be found from the expressions for \bar{R} in the various schemes. Note that, subse-

quently, the expression of rate under SSA for the autocatalysis scheme [eq. (3)] can be rearranged to yield the form

$$(R_\infty - \bar{R})[S]/\bar{R} = K_M - \frac{k_0}{k_1 k_2} (R_\infty - \bar{R})[S] \quad (8)$$

because, in case of autocatalysis (or MM), we find $R_\infty =$

$k_2[E]_0$. It follows from eq. (8) that a plot of $(R_\infty - \bar{R})[\bar{S}]/\bar{R}$ against $(R_\infty - \bar{R})[S]_0$ yields a straight line with *negative* slope. This is clearly shown in Fig. 7. However, for the cooperative

we introduce a graphical approach to circumvent this problem, in particular. Such a distinctive feature would apply to the case of a known oligomeric enzyme as well, where a

Fig. 7. Plot of $(R_\infty - \bar{R})[S]_0/\bar{R}$ against $(R_\infty - \bar{R})[S]_0$ for all the schemes with the two different sets of rate constants shown in (A) and (B). A nonlinear variation marks cooperativity, a horizontal line represents the MM case, while a linear decrease stands for autocatalysis.

kinetics, the plots become non-linear. For example, for the 2-site cooperative scheme, we can write

$$(R_\infty - \bar{R})[\bar{S}]/\bar{R} = f([\bar{S}])(R_\infty - \bar{R})[\bar{S}] \quad (9)$$

Here,

$$f([\bar{S}]) = \frac{K_M K_{M1} + 2K_{M1}[\bar{S}] + [\bar{S}]^2}{R_\infty[\bar{S}]} \times \left(\frac{k_2 K_{M1}}{k_4} + [\bar{S}] \right)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

and $R_\infty = 2k_4[E]_0$. This non-linear nature of the plot is depicted in Fig. 7. As the substrate is in excess, we can replace $[\bar{S}]$ by $[S]_0$ without introducing any significant error. For 3-site cooperativity, $R_\infty = 3k_6[E]_0$ follows. Finally, in the MM case, such a plot will give a horizontal line only, because here we have $k_0 = 0$; this plot, therefore, may as well be used to identify *any kind of* non-MM behavior of the reaction system.

4. Concluding remarks

The standard graphical methods to characterize the nature of enzyme kinetics fail to distinguish autocatalysis (Scheme 2) from positive cooperativity (e.g. Scheme 3 or Scheme 4). When the number of active sites of an enzyme is not known *a priori*, the confusion becomes apparent. Here,

possible alternative to positive cooperativity might be an autocatalytic growth of the only species ES_1 , subject to the restrictions $k_3 \ll k_1$ and $k_4 \ll k_2$ in Scheme 3, while $k_3, k_5 \ll k_1$ and $k_4, k_6 \ll k_2$ in Scheme 4, allowing one to safely disregard the other channels of intermediate and product formation (e.g. via ES_2 or ES_3). Our method should be accurate provided (i) the SSA holds for the intermediate(s) and (ii) R_∞ can be measured with reasonable accuracy. Condition (i) is expected to be maintained for any standard laboratory experiment and consequent modeling of enzyme kinetics. In fact, all the standard plots in literature are based on the validity of SSA. Condition (ii) can also be fulfilled either using direct measurement or extrapolation of rate data^{22,26}. Thus, we believe that, the graphical approach introduced here will be convenient to get a clear distinction between a *direct* autocatalysis¹⁶ and positive cooperativity. Additionally, our prescription can be applied with equal facility to distinguish other non-MM (sigmoidal) cases but with negative effects on the rate, viz. autoinhibition vs negative cooperativity²⁷. We have checked that the first one shows a linear plot whereas the second one depicts a curve, as before. While various works⁵⁻⁷ on cooperativity are available, including some recent reviews^{28,29}, none of them focused attention on the fact that autocatalysis or autoinhibition could be a *comparable potential option*, depending on the situation at hand. As a result, the question of exploring a viable route to decipher the correct mechanism did not arise. This work is a humble endeavor

towards this direction. Future efforts might reveal whether and how far *more complex* autocatalytic processes¹⁶ could be handled by following our route.

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Appendix 1. SS rates for enzymes with multiple conformations

Enzymes with multiple conformations of the unbound state also show characteristic features of MM kinetics for systems reaching equilibrium. The SS rate of product formation for the network in Fig. 8 is given as

$$\bar{R} = \frac{(k_3 + k_4)[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K' + [\bar{S}]} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of the reaction network with the enzyme in two unbound conformations E1 and E2 producing the same product through two routes via the same intermediate ES.

It is evident from eq. (A1) that the rate is in the standard MM form [cf. eq. (1) of the text] that yields hyperbolic kinetics. Here,

$$K' = \frac{K(\gamma + \delta)}{k_1\gamma\delta} \quad (\text{A2})$$

with

$$K = k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_3 + k_4, \quad \gamma = 1 + \frac{k_2\alpha}{k_1\beta}, \quad \delta = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \quad (\text{A3})$$

Appendix 2. Obtaining SS rates for the schemes outlined in Fig. 1

Scheme 1 (MM):

The relevant equations are

$$dC/dt = k_1[E][S] - (k_{-1} + k_2)C, \quad [E] = [E]_0 - C, C \equiv [ES], \quad (\text{A4})$$

and $R = k_2C$. The SSA assumes that $dC/dt = 0$ and thus the SS concentration of the complex is found as

$$\bar{C} = [E]_0[\bar{S}]/(K_M + [\bar{S}]), \quad (\text{A5})$$

while the SS rate becomes

$$\bar{R} = k_2\bar{C} \quad (\text{A6})$$

From (A5) and (A6), eq. (1) of the text emerges.

Scheme 2 (Autocatalysis):

The relevant equations here will be

$$dC/dt = (k_1 + k_0C)[E][S] - (k_{-1} + k_2)C, \quad [E] = [E]_0 - C, C \equiv [ES] \quad (\text{A7})$$

and $R = k_2C$. It is the second part in the first parenthesis of eq. (A7) that takes due care of the autocatalytic growth of the complex. In the SSA, one assumes, as before, that $dC/dt = 0$, and thus the concentration of the complex at SS is found as

$$\bar{C} = [E]_0[\bar{S}]/(K_M + [\bar{S}] - k_0[\bar{E}][\bar{S}]/k_1) \quad (\text{A8})$$

while the SS rate again becomes

$$\bar{R} = k_2\bar{C} \quad (\text{A9})$$

Putting (A8) in (A9), eq. (3) of the main text is obtained.

Scheme 3 (2-site cooperativity):

The following equations are relevant here:

$$\begin{aligned} dC_2/dt &= k_3[S] \cdot C_1 - 2(k_{-3} + k_4)C_2 \\ dC_1/dt &= 2k_1[E][S] - (k_{-1} + k_2)C_1 - dC_2/dt, \\ C_1 &\equiv [ES_1], C_2 \equiv [ES_2], [E] = [E]_0 - C_1 - C_2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A10})$$

and $R = k_2C_1 + 2k_4C_2$. Employing $dC_2/dt = 0$, we first find that

$$\bar{C}_2 = \frac{\bar{C}_1[\bar{S}]}{2K_{M1}} \quad (\text{A11})$$

At the next step, we use the SS conditions $dC_1/dt = 0 = dC_2/dt$ in the second equation that rearranges to yield

$$\bar{C}_1 = \frac{2[E]_0[\bar{S}]}{K_M + 2[\bar{S}] + ([\bar{S}]^2/k_{M1})} \quad (\text{A12})$$

Putting the SS concentrations of the intermediates in the equation

$$\bar{R} = k_2\bar{C}_1 + 2k_4\bar{C}_2 \quad (\text{A13})$$

we get back the desired equation [eq. (4)] of the main text.

Scheme 4 (3-site cooperativity):

The relevant rate equations may be compactly written in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} dC_3/dt &= k_5[S] \cdot C_2 - 3(k_{-5} + k_6)C_3, \\ dC_2/dt &= 2k_3[S] \cdot C_1 - 2(k_{-3} + k_4)C_2 - dC_3/dt, \\ dC_1/dt &= 3k_1[E] \cdot [S] - (k_{-1} + k_2)C_1 - dC_2/dt - dC_3/dt, \\ C_1 &\equiv [ES_1], C_2 \equiv [ES_2], C_3 \equiv [ES_3], \\ [E] &= [E]_0 - C_1 - C_2 - C_3, \end{aligned} \quad (A14)$$

and $R = k_2C_1 + 2k_4C_2 + 3k_6C_3$. Employing respectively $dC_3/dt = 0$, $dC_2/dt = 0$, we evaluate \bar{C}_3 and \bar{C}_2 that lead to

$$\bar{C}_3 = \frac{\bar{C}_2[\bar{S}]}{3K_{M2}}, \bar{C}_2 = \frac{\bar{C}_1[\bar{S}]}{K_{M1}} \quad (A15)$$

Finally, using the above relations and the remaining SS condition that $dC_1/dt = 0$, we obtain from the third condition of eq. (A14)

$$\bar{C}_1 = \frac{3K_{M1}K_{M2}[E]_0 \cdot [\bar{S}]}{K_M K_{M1} K_{M2} + 3K_{M1} K_{M2} [\bar{S}] + 3K_{M2} [\bar{S}]^2 + [\bar{S}]^3} \quad (A16)$$

Inserting expressions (A15) and (A16) for \bar{C}_1 , \bar{C}_2 , etc., in the SS rate eq. (A17) shown below

$$\bar{R} = k_2\bar{C}_1 + 2k_4\bar{C}_2 + 3k_6\bar{C}_3 \quad (A17)$$

we get back the desired eq. (6) of the main text.

Constants K_M , K_{M1} and K_{M2} employed above are defined in Sec. 2 of the main text. When the substrate is in large excess, \bar{C}_2 , \bar{C}_3 , etc. are linked with \bar{C}_1 by constants. Hence, the constancy of \bar{R} implies constancy of all the intermediates, thus ensuring the validity of SSA.

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